

MECHANICAL PROPERTIES AND MICROSTRUCTURE OF CELLULOSE NANOFIBER (CNF) REINFORCED EPOXY

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ABSTRACT

Waterborne epoxy is supposed to be widely used in the field of coating, adhesion and etc. in the future due to the positive characteristics such as environmental-friendliness and easiness to operate. However, it has also been criticised of the relatively low mechanical properties and applicable temperature. In this study, cellulose nanofiber (CNF) is introduced to reinforce the shortcomings above. Benefited by the high aspect ratio, significant mechanical properties of CNF, the new composite material is supposed to acquire better mechanical properties, both on strength and toughness, thermal and dimensional stability, and higher glass transition temperature T_g etc.

Composites containing different content of CNF were prepared from a waterborne epoxy emulsion and a CNF water suspension through mechanical agitation and film casting. Scanning electron microscope was used to observe the dispersion of the filler. Tensile test and tensile shear test were conducted to evaluate the mechanical performance and differential scanning calorimetry test was carried out to measure the glass transition temperature.

The results indicated that low amount of CNF addition had a significant reinforcing effect on waterborne resin including Young's modulus and shear strength. However, no obvious improvement of glass transition temperature is confirmed in CNF reinforced samples.

1 INTRODUCTION

Cellulose is largely spread in plants, bacteria and marine animals which guarantees its great natural reserves. And its traditional industrial usage such as pulp, paper, and filter has a long history. However, the research of cellulose nanofiber (CNF) began from the latest 10 to 20 years and the usage of reinforcement, functional materials etc. starts in the recent several years [1].

Production of CNF could be mainly divided into 3 types, the mechanical, the chemical and the combined method. Through mechanical methods like grinding, collision or water jet of extreme pressure [2] etc., the cellulose is divided into nanoscale. CNF produced from the mechanical method has a bigger size and its suspension usually performs a lower viscosity. In the chemical method, CNF is produced with several kinds of compound acid that are used to promote the hydrolysis of the cellulose and one of the most used is the TEMPO oxidation method invented by Isogai et al. [3], in which filamentous CNF are produced with TEMPO (2,2,6,6-Tetramethylpiperidin-1-yl), sodium bromide, sodium hypochlorite in the aqueous solution. Therefore it is mostly researched as the reinforcing agent or additive to improve viscosity [4]. The combined method is also widely used in the manufacturing of CNF, through which acid is used to hydrolysis the cellulose to a certain degree to reduce the difficulty of mechanical defibrillation. And CNF with its 6th primary hydroxyl group transferred into carboxymethyl group is known as the cellulose nanocrystal (CMC). CMC is usually rod-like. CMC possesses with many unique characteristics such as superior optical property, self-assembling and outstanding gas barrier ability [5]. As a result, no matter what kind of method is used, the product CNF possesses the merits such as high aspect ratio, specific surface area, light transmittance, viscosity, and excellent mechanical properties like high specific strength (with a Young's modulus of about 140 GPa and a strength of 3 GPa, which is as strong as iron while the weight is only 1/5 of the iron) and dimensional stability (with a coefficient

of thermal expansion of about 0.1 ppm/K, which is comparable with quartz glass) etc., making it a prosperous material in the field of additive, reinforcing agent [6].

Recent years, researches on CNF reinforced composite is carried out steadily where CNF is introduced in hydrophobic resin to make structural materials that are light but of high performance. Considering the characteristics that there are quantities of hydroxyl group on the surface of CNF, it is rather difficult to disperse CNF in organic solvents. Some methods are proved to be feasible such as surface modification by derivatization, electrostatic interaction or physical interlocking to cover CNF with hydrophobic compounds. However, problems like the insufficient affinity or strength on the interface remains to be solved [7].

On the other hand, waterborne resin, which is also a potential material due to its low content of volatile organic compounds (VOCs), easiness to operate and a relatively good chemical resistance [8]. Considering the growing needs of environment protection and low toxicity, waterborne resin is considered to be a prospective substitute of solvent-based resin. It is worthwhile to illustrate the reinforcing effect of CNF to waterborne resin. Since both the matrix and the CNF are hydrophilic, the dispersion between them is no longer a problem. Their affinity and strength in the interface is better than the solvent in consideration that there are also hydrogen bonds that exist in the interface.

Although there are several methods to keep epoxy water-soluble, their cured products are with no exception on a low degree of polymerization. Therefore, it is not always capable in severe environment where high mechanical properties and wide applicable temperature is needed. In this study, CNF is introduced as a reinforcing agent and several experiment are carried out to evaluate the performance of this new composite coating.

2 EXPERIMENT PART

2.1 MATERIALS

The stable suspension of cellulose nanofiber was used as the starting material, which is made by the high pressure water jet method and supplied by SUGINO MACHINE Ltd., Uozu, Toyama, Japan. A part of the detail of this material is shown as below. Concentration: 2 wt. %, viscosity: over 3000 MPa•s, specific surface area: 100~200 m²/g, degree of polymerization: 200~550 and the fiber is shaped in a diameter of about 20 nanometer and a length of a few micrometer.

2 different waterborne resins were used as the matrix of the composite. (a) vinyl-modified epoxy ester resin emulsion. The emulsion consists of 40 wt. % of solid content, 58.4 wt. % of water and the rest 1.6 wt. % of organic solvent and amine. (b) epoxy-modified alkyd emulsion, in which about 41 wt. % of solid content is contained. Both of the waterborne resins are one-pack type and cure through polycondensation.

2.2 HOMOGENIZATION AND FILM FORMING

The matrix suspension and CNF suspension prepared in 5 different mass fraction ratios (0 wt. %, 2.5 wt. %, 5 wt. %, 10 wt. %, 20 wt. %) and later stirred under 300 rpm for 15 minutes using an magnetic stirrer (AS ONE RS-1AN). This stirring condition is confirmed to be effective by comparing scanning electron micrograph with a specimen made under 1000rpm for 5 minutes, which shows the affinity between 2 materials. This colloid mixture was then coated on substrates using a film applicator with thickness specifications of 75 μm, 150 μm, 250 μm, 500 μm, 750 μm and 1000 μm, in which higher thickness were used in the preparation of test pieces for evaluations of mechanical properties. Coatings are cured in the circumstance of 40°C for 2 days until the weight keeps still.

2.3 THERMAL ANALYSIS

Differential scanning calorimetry (Shimadzu DSC-60) was used to detect the glass transition temperature T_g of the cured composite. The standard sample contained about 2 mg of Aluminum oxide and the others were loaded with 2 mg of pieces of cured film consisted of neat waterborne epoxy, waterborne epoxy reinforced with 2.5 wt. % and 20 wt. % of CNF, respectively.

The test was performed in the inert atmosphere of argon gas and both the standard sample and the DSC device was set to heat at a rate of 20 K/s from room temperature to 373.15 K and preserved for

120 s. Then samples were cooled to 253.15 K at a rate of 10 K/s using liquid nitrogen as a refrigerant.

After the temperature remained stable at 253 K, the test pieces were scanned again at a rate of 20 K/s to 373 K. The heat flow-temperature curve of the later scanning is used to analyze the glass transition point.

2.4 MORPHOLOGY CHARACTERIZATION

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) was performed on test pieces in order to reveal the dispersion state of the composite. Both the surface and the cross-section are observed using a Keyence VE-7800 SEM and the acceleration voltage is restricted under 3 kV considering the low electrical conduction of the coating.

2.5 TENSILE TEST AND TENSILE SHEAR TEST

Tensile tests were performed on Imada compact tensile/compression testing machine to reveal the Young's modulus of the composite coating. Mixture colloid was coated on both sides of the PET thin film in a thickness of 500 μm . As there is no specific standard applicable for this test, non-standard substrate that refers to the 13th non-proportional test piece in the Japan Industrial Standard JIS Z 2201:1998 to a certain degree is made, and considering the test condition, the substrate size is set as 50 mm \times 10 mm \times 0.19 mm, and the gauge length L is 35 mm, as is shown in Fig.1 (a). And the thickness of the cured test pieces are summarized in Table 1. Particularly, the thickness in Table 1 means the summation of the substrate and the coating. The thickness is measured 5 times using a micrometer and the average is calculated.

CNF wt.%	substrate	0	2.5	5.0	10.0	20.0	30.0
Thickness/mm	0.130	0.370	0.253	0.230	0.210	0.196	0.184

Table 1: Details of the test pieces used in tensile test.

Tensile shear tests were performed on the same test machine to clarify the maximum strength of the material. Test pieces are prepared following the JIS K 6850:1999 standard, which is shown in Fig.1 (b).

Figure 1: Shape of the substrates used in tensile test (a) and tensile shear test (b).

Both of the tests were carried out in the room environment (at a temperature of 20~25 °C and a relative humidity that ranges between 25~40 %) and deformation speed was set as 0.015 mm/s.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 MICROSTRUCTURE AND DISPERSION OF THE COMPOSITE FILM

Several specimens consisting of 80 wt. % of waterborne epoxy ester resin and 20 wt. % of CNF were observed and confirmed that CNF was dispersed homogeneously and a set of typical scanning electron micrographs are shown in Fig. 1. Although it is difficult to tell the exact length of a single CNF, it is likely that the length is no shorter than 50 μm and most of the fibers possess a diameter of less than 100 nm. Still, some aggregated fibers are confirmed to be of a diameter of about 1~2 μm .

Figure 2: Scanning electron micrograph of a surface of a composite film in which (a)~(b) are of a specimen reinforced with 5 wt. % of CNF, (c)~(d) are of a specimen reinforced with 20 wt. % of CNF

3 set of cross-section scanning electronic micrographs were also shown in Fig. 3 to illustrate the relationship between the cross-sectional morphology and the CNF weight percent.

Figure 3: Scanning electron micrograph of a cross-section of a composite resin, in which (a)~(c) are specimens reinforced with 20 wt. % of CNF, (d)~(f) are specimens reinforced with 40 wt. % of CNF

The cross-section of film reinforced by 20 wt. % of CNF has a resin-like morphology. Some scraps of aggregated CNF with a maximum diameter of 1~20 μm are observed on the cross-section, most of

the CNF are dispersed with the resin matrix intensively and homogeneously to form a 3 dimensional network structure.

Composite film consisting of 40 wt. % of CNF showed a different cross-sectional morphology as is shown in Fig. 3(d) ~ (f). Instead of being transparent and resin-like, the cross-section has a characteristic of layered structure. Every layer is covered with resin and between layers some micrometer level interspace was observed.

3.2 GLASS TRANSITION TEMPERATURE

The result of DSC test is summarized in Fig. 4. All of the 3 samples, which contain neat waterborne epoxy, waterborne epoxy with 2.5 wt. % and 20 wt. % of CNF, respectively performed a characteristic curve of T_g at about 274.65 K, which is marker with a red line. As there is no glass transition point in CNF [3], the DSC test run on neat CNF was not covered here.

Although it was considered the addition of CNF would increase the glass transition temperature by restricting the molecular motion through the 3-dimensional network structure. However in this case, it is considered that there is a lack of strong bond between the interface of CNF and the matrix resin. Even though CNF is dispersed in a 3-dimensional structure inside the matrix resin, it failed to work as a stabilizer to increase the glass transition temperature.

Figure 4: Differential scanning calorimetry data used to detect glass transition temperature.

3.3 TENSILE TEST

The Young's modulus was calculated by equation 1 using the data of plastic deformation in tensile test as is shown in Fig. 5, where the composite film deformed plastically together with the substrate.

Figure 5: Tensile load-displacement curve of tensile test.

$$F = \left(\frac{A_0}{L} E_0 + \frac{A_i}{L} E_i \right) x \quad (1)$$

Where F is the tensile load (N), A_0 is the substrate's sectional area (mm^2), which equals to 1.3 mm^2 in this test, A_i is the composite coating's sectional area (mm^2). L is the gauge length (mm) of the test piece, which equals to 35 mm in this test. E_0 is the substrate's Young's modulus (MPa), E_i is the composite coatings' Young's modulus (MPa). And x is the displacement (mm) of test pieces.

The relationship between Young's modulus and CNF weight percent was concluded in Fig. 6. Young's modulus of the initial matrix resin itself is too low to measure, it is still an alternative when the request is not so severe.

Figure 6: The relationship between Young's modulus and CNF weight percentage.

Scanning electron micrograph is taken on a 20 wt. % CNF reinforced waterborne epoxy ester test piece after the tensile test is done and is shown in Fig. 7.

Figure 7: Scanning electron micrograph of tensile test specimens

A large number of micro notches and holes of different directions can be observed on the surface of the specimen, as there used to be filled with CNF. It can be inferred that CNF is pulled out during the tensile test and local stress in one direction is dispersed due to the network structure of CNF which helps to reduce the stress concentration in the composite.

3.4 TENSILE SHEAR TEST

The shear strength measured in the tensile shear test is shown in Fig. 8 in which (a)(c)(e) show the relationship between the shear strength and the CNF addition in waterborne ester resin matrix while (b)(d)(f) show the relationship in waterborne epoxy modified alkyd resin. Still the summary of maximum shear strength is shown in Fig. 9.

Figure 8: Tensile shear strength-strain curve of matrix and CNF reinforced composite. ((a),(b): matrix only, including epoxy ester and epoxy modified alkyd; (c) epoxy ester reinforced by 5 wt. % of CNF; (d) epoxy modified alkyd reinforced with 2.5 wt. % of CNF; (e) epoxy ester reinforced with 20 wt. % of CNF; (f) epoxy modified alkyd reinforced with 20 wt. % of CNF.)

Figure 9: Maximum strength of composite with different CNF weight percent

In both of the waterborne resin, the addition of a few amount of CNF results in significant growth in maximum shear strength whereas in higher amount like 20 wt. %, the maximum shear strength decreases and the behavior after the stress peak is totally different as waterborne epoxy ester reinforced by 20 wt. % of CNF ruptured instantly after the peak and waterborne epoxy modified alkyd

containing 20 wt. % showed a similar tendency while all the specimens reinforced by low amounts of CNF ended up without rupturing but instead remaining bonded and performed a strength close to specimens consisting of matrix resin only.

Figure 10: Fracture surface observation of tensile shear specimens.

As is shown in Fig. 10, except for epoxy ester with 20 wt.% of CNF (Fig. 9(b)), composite resin is found remained on both sides of the substrates, with quantities of concave-convex due of the shear force. Still, though epoxy modified alkyd resin reinforced with 20 wt.% of CNF is found left on both of the substrates, it had shown a tendency of separation on surface as half of the substrate is not covered with the composite resin. The result corresponds with the behaviors shown in Fig. 7 that the shear strength of 20 wt. % CNF reinforced epoxy ester dropped to 0 soon after the strength peak.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The purpose of this study was to introduce an environmental-friendly composite resin capable in relatively severe environment by adding a small amount of CNF and therefore the reinforcing effect in mechanical properties and glass transition point of CNF in waterborne resin is presented.

The composite of waterborne resin and CNF was made through mechanical agitation at a speed of 300 rpm for 15 minutes. The cured composite resin was observed on SEM to illustrate the dispersion of CNF. Except for some local agitation, the CNF was well dispersed in the structure of 3-dimensional network and through SEM observation of tensile test piece, micro notches and holes in irregular directions were found, which led to the assumption that the 3-dimensional network structure helps to transfer and rebalance the local stress concentration. However, when the stress surpasses the Van de Waal's force on the CNF-resin interface, the CNF was pulled out, leaving quantities of micro notches and holes. As a result, it was considered necessary to strengthen the interfacial adhesive strength through chemical crosslinking.

In differential scanning calorimetry test, it was illustrated that there is no difference in glass transition temperature between neat resin and CNF reinforced resin probably because of the lack of strong bond at the interface of CNF and resin.

Influences of the CNF addition to mechanical properties were illustrated in tensile test and tensile shear test. In the tensile test, it was found that Young's modulus increased significantly with the increase of CNF addition. Still the Young's module is found increasing faster after 20 wt. %. It is probably because more CNF-CNF interface linked by hydrogen bond were generated, which was stronger than the Van de Waal's force in the CNF-resin interface.

In tensile shear test, waterborne epoxy ester resin of relatively high strength and waterborne epoxy modified alkyd which were of relatively low strength are used to obtain the shear strength of the composite material. In the case that few amount of CNF was introduced, the strength increased by 7 times or more. However, 20 wt. % of CNF addition led to a lower strength and the stress-strain curve shows a different behavior which was more brittle-like after the peak point.

It could also be inferred that when the waterborne resin reinforced by low amounts of CNF get loaded, the 3-dimensional network of CNF affects to transfer the local stress concentration. However, as the CNF-resin interface bonded by Van de Waal's force was weak, when the stress increase to a certain point that exceeds the stress transfer ability of CNF, CNF starts to be dragged out from the matrix resin. And the resin reinforced by low amount of CNF showed almost the same stress as the neat resin in the last part of the tensile shear strength-strain curve, which was considered that most of the CNF was dragged out from the matrix. As for epoxy ester resin reinforced by 20 wt.% of CNF, the shear strength dropped to 0 instantly after the peak because the rupture at the interface of the composite resin and the substrate occurred. It was considered that the addition of CNF decreased the adhesion between the composite resin and the substrate. And another reason is that although matrix resin of high stiffness is less affected by the CNF aggregation before the stress peak, once the crack was generated, the growth of the crack became unstoppable, which could also be inferred from the difference of the fracture shown in Fig.10(b) and Fig.10(d).

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